

THE CULTURAL AND EDUCATIONAL RELATIONS OF THE STATES OF UZBEKISTAN AND KAZAKHSTAN IN THE EARLY YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE

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Abstract. *This article provides information about the political, cultural and educational relations between the states of Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan in the early period of independence. These data were analyzed based on scientific sources and conclusions were given.*

Keywords: *independence, Uzbekistan, diplomacy, Kazakhstan, cultural, educational, Central Asia, Turkestan.*

INTRODUCTION

Representatives of related nations have been living in the historical region called Turkestan for centuries. In this political term, which is called Central Asia today, there are five independent republics.

Central Asia refers to the five Muslim republics that gained independence after the collapse of the Soviet Union: Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan. During the Soviet period, the terms of Central Asia and Kazakhstan were applied to this region. However, after gaining independence in 1991, both these countries and foreign countries began to use the term Central Asia. In 1992, the leaders of five countries adopted the term Central Asia at an official meeting[1]. Currently, this term is accepted by the world community. Central Asian departments have been opened in most international organizations and research institutes. However, from the point of view of the geographical Central Asian region, Central Asia also includes Afghanistan, Mongolia, and the Uighur regions of China.

The dictatorship of the former Soviet Union (USSR), which lasted more than a century, came to an end in 1989-1991. Independent democratic republics were established in Central Asia. After independence, extensive relations were established between the neighboring republics. Special attention was paid to the cultural and educational spheres. Great results have been achieved in the cultural and educational sphere for 32 years[2].

Figure 1. *Relations between Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan.*

The practice of the President of the State addressing the Parliament every year exists in many countries of the world. It defines strategic goals and tasks to be implemented in the near future. For the first time in the history of Uzbekistan, the President of our republic, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, addressed the Oliy Majlis in December 2017 and noted that the priority direction of foreign policy is constructive dialogue with close neighbors and conducting a strong foreign policy[3]. At the same time, in the speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the international conference on Central Asia: unified history and common future, cooperation for sustainable development and development held in Samarkand, Our main goal is a common effort - is to turn Central Asia into a stable, economically developed and highly developed region with our efforts. For this, we need to jointly eliminate the causes and factors that cause and contribute to various conflicts, and ensure national development based on regional priority interests. He emphasized that today we are looking for a rational compromise to solve acute regional issues such as the border, water use, transport and trade, realizing the common priorities of our development.

METHODS

In the article, on the basis of the principles of objectivity, historical analysis, comparative-logical analysis, chronological sequence, devoted to the specific relations of the states of Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan in the cultural and educational sphere in the first years of independence, it is covered on the basis of scientific sources consists of.

RESULTS

Culture is a certain level of historical development of society, human creative power and abilities. It is expressed in various forms of people's life and activities, as well as in the material and spiritual wealth they create. Cultural and educational processes between peoples serve to strengthen the concepts of affection, friendship, brotherhood, and brotherhood among people.

The cultural processes of the countries of Central Asia have been inextricably linked with each other since ancient times. For example, there are a number of cultural and historical documents proving that the Uzbek and Kazakh nations have the same origin. These include “Orhun”, “Enisei” inscriptions, findings found on the banks of the Talas rivers, Mahmud Kashgari “Devonu lug'atit turk”, Yusuf Balasuguni “Qutatgu bilik”, Anmad Yugnaki “Hibatul hakoyik”, Works such as Zahriddin Muhammad Babur “Baburnoma”, Abulghozi Bahadirkhan “Turk Shajaras”, Muhammad Haydar Dulati “Tarihi Rashid”, Bebaris and Khaldun “Kipchak Shajaras”, Osman Kohistan “Tarihi Abulkhairi” and “Korqit Ota”, “Shaiboniynoma”, “Zafarnoma”, “Alpomish”, “Goroghli” and many other heritages of folk art can be given as an example.

The ancient friendship, neighborly ties, and mutual cooperation between Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan, located in the heart of the Asian continent and the Great Silk Road, spread to the distant layers of history.

We are very happy that hundreds of thousands of our Kazakh citizens, who live peacefully in our multi-ethnic country, make a significant contribution to all the successes achieved by independent Uzbekistan. Among them there are many elected representatives of the Parliament of Uzbekistan and local authorities, as well as leaders of various levels.

In the years of independence, more than 600 Kazakh citizens of Uzbekistan have been awarded high state awards and titles, which is a confirmation of the fact that they have made a worthy contribution to the development of our country and are widely recognized and respected by our people[4]. In raising the spiritual culture of the nations, the joint study of the cultural

heritage that belongs to all of them, the lives and works of historical figures, had a great impact on the friendship of peoples and the deepening of inter-ethnic relations. Further deepening of the cooperation of the Central Asian countries, increasing their effectiveness has brought about the historical unity of the peoples of these countries, reconsideration with true scientific and theoretical conclusions, cooperation of industries and sectors. In this regard, one of the first promising steps is to expand the scope of the tasks and activities of the International Association for the Cooperation and Development of the Peoples of Central Asia and Kazakhstan (MASSPN), which was established in Tashkent in 1992[5]. The Treaty on friendship, cooperation and mutual assistance between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Kazakhstan, presented by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and signed in Turkestan on June 24, 1992, has been ratified[6].

The association helped to develop the processes of integration in the economic and cultural spheres, taking into account the needs of the population of the multi-ethnic region, strengthening the friendly practical relations between countries, regions, districts and public organizations.

The creation of the newspaper “Yangi Kun” and its publication in Uzbek, Russian, Tajik, and Kyrgyz languages helped bring the views and aspirations of the region's residents closer together, deepening national and interethnic relations.

Negotiations were held between the two countries on January 10, 1994 in Tashkent. An agreement and a number of documents were signed on further development of cooperation in education, culture, healthcare, tourism, and sports.

In 1994, the festival of creativity of the peoples of Uzbekistan was opened in Tashkent. The conference dedicated to the three years of independence of our country was organized by the Republican International Cultural Center. The ceremony was held in one of the most beautiful palaces in our capital - Turkistan. The guests were welcomed by representatives of the Kazakh cultural center of the republic. In addition to representatives of Kazakh cultural centers in the regions of Uzbekistan, friends from Kazakhstan, activists of other national cultural centers in the capital of our republic, cultural figures of the two republics were invited to the celebration. A big concert was also dedicated to the many captive friendships of the neighboring nations. Bilingual songs, lapars, and tunes by Kazakh and Uzbek composers were played there. On May 23, 1994, the opening ceremony of Kazakhstan Days was held in Tashkent. In this regard, the visit of guests in our capital and regions did not stop. First, they laid wreaths on the statue of the great Allama Ahmad Fargani, who visited Fergana region. The symbol of the city of Fergana - Independence Gate was visited. Days of Kazakhstan became a real holiday in Karakalpakstan. A ceremony dedicated to Days of Kazakhstan was held in the Nukus Art Palace named after Berdak. Cultural relations took on a traditional character.

The works of Chokhan Valikhonov, Abay, Jambul, Mukhtar Avezov, Sobit Mukhanov, Anvar Olimjanov, Olmas Sulaymanov and other Kazakh creators were translated into Uzbek and Karakalpakstan. At the same time, the works of Aibek, Gafur Ghulam, and Mirtemir were published in the Kazakh language and delivered to readers.

On the occasion of the Kazakhstan Days, the Avezov academic drama theater group in Almaty staged the performances “Malikai Turondot” and “He called the poor man walking on the street to be a governor”. At the end of 1995, a congress of representatives of Central Asian intellectuals was held in Tashkent. Maskur Anjuman was a great event in terms of revival of our common history, culture and traditions of our peoples.

The first congress of the “Assembly of Cultural Figures of the Peoples of the Central Asian Countries” was held in 1996. During the meeting with the film artists, the president of the assembly, Chingiz Aymatov, expressed his opinion on strengthening cooperation. At the assembly, representatives of film personalities discussed the issues of developing a plan for the further development of regional film art. At the meeting, it was agreed to restore the famous Tashkent International Film Festival and to hold it annually in the capitals of five neighboring countries, and to organize a documentary film festival every two years in Samarkand, to organize seminars in the regional film associations and creative organizations received[7].

On August 23, 1996, in Almaty, the capital of Kazakhstan, the President of Uzbekistan and members of the delegation participated in the celebrations dedicated to the 150th anniversary of the birth of the famous Kazakh nobleman Jambul Jabayev. We can see on the basis of various examples that during these years, along with many other fields, especially in the field of science and culture, Uzbekistan-Kazakhstan relations have expanded. In particular, until 1996, 107 joint projects were prepared in 16 priority areas of science and technology[8]. In 1997, in the city of Samarkand, a group of famous artists of the brotherly Kazakh nation took part in the international music festival “Sharq Taronalari” along with representatives of majority countries. In fact, their songs are not new for us. Because Uzbek and Kazakh art have been drinking water from the same spring since ancient times, and their joint jihads are countless. Moreover, when an Uzbek gets married, the dead of the Kazakh stream bring grace to the circle. Salt and salt to the Kazakh people, the Uzbek bakhshi epic will flood people with thermals. Talented Kazakh singers such as Ramazon Stamghoziyev, Bekbulat Tleukhanov, Uljon Boybusinova, Beruk Jusupov, Yerjon Kosbarmakov performed with their songs.

DISCUSSION

According to statistical data, there are one million Uzbeks living in Kazakhstan, and more than one million Kazakhs living in Uzbekistan. There are 605 Kazakh schools in Uzbekistan, where 15,000 children study. Tashkent State Pedagogical University, Syrdaryo, Jizzakh, Nukus, and Navoi Pedagogical Institutes have started to work in Kazakh language departments. The Council of Kazakh Literature was established under the Union of Writers in Uzbekistan, and the Kazakh theater studio “Kok-Tem” was established in Jizzakh region.

On October 31, 1998, the Treaty of Eternal Friendship between the countries of Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan served to further strengthen cultural ties between the countries. Because it was determined to be implemented in accordance with the inter-institutional agreement on cooperation in the field of education between the Ministry of Education, Culture and Health. This indicates that cultural relations have reached another level. Uzbekistan is on the way to developing relations based on mutual trust and good neighborliness with Kazakhstan. The Uzbek and Kazakh peoples, not only as close neighbors, but also as brothers, have long understood and supported each other on all issues of multilateral cooperation.

The countries are walking shoulder to shoulder on the path of development as good neighbors and mutually beneficial partners.

In particular, in the last five years, the volume of mutual trade has more than doubled, and by the end of this year it will reach five billion dollars. It was agreed to create a working group under the leadership of the Deputy Prime Ministers and establish a joint foreign trade company in order to increase the mutual supply of products in high demand in the coming years.

The state visit of the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to Kazakhstan on March 22-23, 2017 and the state visit of the President of Kazakhstan Kassim-Jomart Tokayev to Uzbekistan on April 14-15, 2019 became a strong impetus for cooperation at a new stage. As a result of these visits, more than 20 intergovernmental and interdepartmental documents, as well as agreements on trade and economic cooperation, were signed.

Figure 2. Official meeting of the President of Kazakhstan Kassim-Jomart Tokayev and the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

SUMMARY

In conclusion, relations between Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan are aimed at strengthening cultural cooperation and friendship. It has been establishing cooperation between peoples in equal and mutual cultural and educational events, and has been implementing measures to strengthen and develop it step by step.

Strengthening friendship and good neighborliness with Kazakhstan is one of the most important priorities of Uzbekistan's foreign policy.

Our countries support each other in international policy issues and cooperate effectively within the framework of UN, SCO, CIS, Economic Cooperation Organization, Organization of Islamic Cooperation, Organization of Turkic States, International Fund for Island Rescue and other international organizations. The positions of the parties on many issues of regional and international importance are similar or close.

Kazakhstan is one of the important trade and economic partners of Uzbekistan. In the last five years, trade between our countries has been growing steadily despite the consequences of the pandemic. In January-November 2022, this figure was 4.2 billion US dollars.

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